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Optimizing Dementia Diagnosis through Distance-Correlation Feature Space and Dimensionality Reduction

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The reduction of dimensionality in Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence problems constitutes a pivotal element in the simplification of models, significantly enhancing both their performance and execution time. This process enables the generation of results more rapidly while also facilitating the scalability and optimization of systems that rely on such models. Two primary approaches are commonly employed to achieve dimensionality reduction: feature selection-based methods and those grounded in feature extraction. In the present paper, we propose a Distance-Correlation Feature Space, upon which we define a dimensionality reduction algorithm based on space transformations and Graph Embeddings. This methodology is applied in the context of dementia diagnosis through learning models, with the overarching objective of optimizing the diagnostic process.

Keywords: Dimensionality reduction; Distance-Correlation; Graph Embeddings; Dementia Diagnosis

1. Introduction

Dimensionality reduction represents one of the main areas of study within data preprocessing techniques that underpin subsequent Machine Learning methods. The increase in the volume of data¹⁻³ and its dimensionality results in the generation of massive datasets, which are subsequently used by supervised and unsupervised models. The computational cost associated with Machine Learning and data analysis algorithms is considerably high, with most exceeding $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$ and others easily reaching $\mathcal{O}(n^4)$ in the worst cases,⁴ and when combined with the large volume of data, this leads to significant temporal costs, rendering such models impractical for use in rapid response

systems, such as real-time applications.

Cognitive impairments diseases (such as Dementia or Alzheimer) represent a significant challenge in healthcare, affecting the daily functioning of individuals and serving as potential indicators of neurodegenerative diseases. Early and accurate classification of cognitive impairments is crucial for timely intervention and treatment planning. However, the complexity and heterogeneity of cognitive decline make traditional diagnostic approaches challenging. In the fields of medicine and neuroscience, Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques are increasingly used in the development of tools capable of diagnosing,⁵⁻¹⁰ and even helping to explain symptoms that a patient

may exhibit. A significant portion of the research focuses on the application of AI in the automated classification of Alzheimer's Disease (AD). Several studies employ deep learning models, such as convolutional neural networks (CNN), to analyze medical imaging data, particularly magnetic resonance imaging (MRI).^{10,11} These models demonstrate high accuracy in distinguishing between different cognitive states, such as cognitively normal (CN), early mild cognitive impairment (EMCI), and late mild cognitive impairment (LMCI). Some studies emphasize the importance of model explainability, employing techniques such as Grad-CAM to visualize critical regions in brain scans that contribute to classification decisions.¹¹ Furthermore, ensemble machine learning models have been proposed as an alternative to deep learning, achieving comparable or even superior performance in AD classification while requiring less training data.¹⁰

Furthermore, an alternative line of research investigates the potential of electroencephalography (EEG) as a non-invasive and cost-effective tool for Alzheimer's diagnosis.¹²⁻¹⁶ These studies propose methodologies that use wavelet coherence and functional connectivity analysis to identify alterations in brain activity associated with neurodegeneration. In particular, the feasibility of using a reduced EEG montage with only four channels is explored, demonstrating accuracy comparable to traditional multi-channel setups.¹³ This finding suggests a promising avenue for portable and accessible early-stage diagnosis solutions. In addition, wavelet coherence models have been employed to analyze cortical connectivity with high temporal resolution, revealing significant differences in coherence patterns between AD patients and healthy controls.¹²

Beyond machine learning applications, another set of studies reviews the role of multimodal imaging techniques and advanced classification algorithms in improving the precision of Alzheimer's disease detection.¹⁷ These reviews highlight the importance of integrating different imaging modalities, such as MRI and positron emission tomography (PET), to develop robust diagnostic biomarkers. More recent and powerful classification techniques, such as enhanced probabilistic neural networks, have been suggested to improve detection accuracy. Furthermore, research on graph-based complexity metrics has explored their applicability to detect neurodegener-

ative disorders by analyzing brain connectivity.¹⁸ These studies propose new complexity measures, such as Graph Index Complexity and Off-Diagonal Complexity, which have been successfully applied to both aging-related conditions and autism spectrum disorder.

Overall, these studies underscore the critical role of AI-driven methodologies in cognitive impairment research. However, high-dimensional data often lead to overfitting and reduced interpretability. Our study addresses this limitation by proposing a dimensionality reduction framework that enhances classification accuracy while preserving the interpretability of key cognitive features.

In the healthcare domain, the challenge of interpretability is of paramount importance, as decisions cannot be effectively made if they are not articulated in comprehensible terms. A doctor cannot rely on a decision that lacks a clear explanation, and similarly, a patient is unlikely to have confidence in a specialist who relies on results derived solely from computational methods.^{19,20} Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI)^{11,21-23} focuses on this last aspect, striving to create models that aid in the attribution of importance values to the features used. This approach facilitates an understanding of the significance and relevance of certain attributes in the context of the problem, as well as potential interactions between them and the target variable, among other factors. In this paper, a new method is proposed on reduction in dimensionality through the Distance-Correlation Feature Space (DCFS) and Graph Embedding, to correspond to the XAI field. Distance correlation provides a more informative measure of the relationships between features, taking into account both linear and nonlinear dependencies. This allows for a more meaningful feature space, where feature importance can be more accurately assessed. The use of graph embeddings translates feature relationships into a Euclidean space, making patterns and dependencies among variables more interpretable. The dimensionality reduction algorithm selectively merges highly related features while preserving their contribution to the model, simplifying the decision-making process, and improving the interpretability of the final predictions.

In summary, in this paper we present a new method of dimensionality reduction in problems applied to the diagnosis of cognitive impairment dis-

eases. Dimensionality reduction has the following advantages in the study of this type of disease: (1) Ability to eliminate variables that have no causal relationship with the objective. In this case, it may imply a reduction in the number of diagnostic tests. (2) It allows for the creation of less complex models with greater explanatory capacity. The paper analyzes the results of being applied to two well-known public datasets: OASIS-2^{24,25} dataset and the UDS (Uniform Data Set) dataset from the National Alzheimer’s Coordinating Center (NACC).^{26–28}

2. Related work

2.1. Dimensionality reduction algorithms

Dimensionality reduction techniques are divided into two main categories: feature selection and feature extraction.²⁹ Techniques based on feature selection are often linked to explainability,^{30,31} as they involve preliminary analyses of attribute importance, which requires understanding of the relevance of each attribute to determine its inclusion or exclusion. On the other hand, dimensionality reduction methods based on feature extraction,^{32,33} such as Principal Component Analysis (PCA),^{34,35} produce sets of transformed variables that generate lower-dimensional spaces, often at the expense of the original meaning of the variables. This is because new variables are created during the transformation process, without directly selecting from the original set. Identifying a way to reduce dimensionality through transformations requires that such transformations be grounded in the relationships between the original attributes, which implicitly demands a prior understanding of both the interactions and importance of these variables.

In this paper, we propose the definition of a novel feature space, termed Distance-Correlation Feature Space, upon which we introduce a dimensionality reduction algorithm based on transformations of the original data, leveraging Graph Embedding techniques. Previous studies have explored the potential of using Graph Embedding techniques³⁶ to identify groups of interacting variables in medical applications, such as the detection of dementia through Machine Learning.

In the present work, the authors define a flexible methodology that projects the attributes of a

dataset - containing information on patients with and without dementia - onto a Euclidean space via a Graph Embedding algorithm, creating a vector representation that encodes the relationships between the variables as distances in this space. This vector representation in the embedding allows the application of classical data analysis and Machine Learning techniques, from which results are derived to identify groups of variables that exhibit similar behavior or impact predictive models in comparable ways.

2.2. Graph Embeddings

Graph embedding techniques refer to a set of approaches that enable the representation of information stored in a graph within a δ -dimensional Euclidean space (typically of low dimension).^{37–39} The goal is to vectorize a graph such that each vertex is represented as a point (vector) in the embedding space. Classical data analysis and Artificial Intelligence techniques can then be applied to these embeddings. Among the most popular approaches for building embeddings are those based on factorization, random walks, and neural networks.

3. Theory background

The study of graph analysis has significantly advanced in the realm of Machine Learning, with graph embedding techniques playing a critical role in transforming graphs into a δ -dimensional space. This transformation simplifies the application of algorithms for tasks such as classification, regression, and clustering.

Various methodologies have been proposed for the generation of graph embeddings, with the primary ones outlined in a review of graph embedding techniques.⁴⁰ These methods are largely based on factorization, random walks, or deep learning. Our work specifically explores factorization-based approaches, with a focus on their potential applications in medicine and explainable AI (XAI).

Factorization-based graph embedding algorithms first emerged in the 2000s, with the aim of representing each graph node as a vector and reducing dimensionality. One such algorithm is Local Linear Embedding (LLE),⁴¹ which utilized a quadratic objective function built from a neighborhood graph and solved it by calculating its eigenvectors.

3.1. Laplacian Eigenmaps

The LLE principle was first introduced by the Laplacian Eigenmaps⁴² in 1971, where the idea behind the embedding problem was to optimize the following equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_x J(x) &= \sum_{i=1}^{|\mathcal{V}|} \sum_{j=1}^{|\mathcal{V}|} \|x_i - x_j\|^2 w_{ij}, \\ \text{s.t.}, \sum_{i=1}^{|\mathcal{V}|} \|x_i\|^2 &= 1, \sum_{i=1}^{|\mathcal{V}|} x_i = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where x_i and x_j are vectors of the embedding space δ -dimensional and w_{ij} are the associated weights between the nodes i and j . The constraints defined for the optimization problem avoid making every $x_i = 0$. The main idea behind equation (1) is that the large distances between pairs of vectors x_i and x_j in the embedding space correspond to small weights w_{ij} in the original graph (associated with the edge e_{ij} that connects the nodes v_i and v_j) and vice versa.

This property is commonly referred to as the *local topology preserving* and mathematically is defined as follows:

$$\text{if } w_{ij} \geq w_{pq} \rightarrow (x_i - x_j)^2 \leq (x_p - x_q)^2, \forall i, j, p, q \quad (2)$$

This basically states that the larger (or smaller) a weight w_{ij} is in the original graph, the closer (or farther) x_i and x_j should be in the embedding space. The usual approach required to solve the optimization problem presented in equation (1) is based primarily on the eigendecomposition of the Laplacian matrix (3) representing the graph. Mathematically:

$$\begin{aligned} L_{ij} &\triangleq \begin{cases} \text{deg}(v_i) & \text{if } i = j \\ -1 & \text{if } i \neq j \text{ and } v_i \text{ is adjacent to } v_j \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ L &= D - W \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where D is the diagonal matrix that contains the degree of each corresponding vertex and W is the adjacency matrix with the graph weights.

The Laplacian Eigenmap embedding will be computed as follows:

(1) Compute the laplacian matrix for the original

graph:

$$L = D - W$$

(2) Normalize the laplacian matrix with the following:

$$\hat{L}_{ij} \triangleq \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i = j \text{ and } k_i \neq 0 \\ -\frac{1}{\sqrt{k_i k_j}} & \text{if } i \neq j \text{ and } \text{adjacent}(n_i, n_j) \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$\hat{L} = (D^+)^{1/2} L (D^+)^{1/2}$$

where k_i represents the degree of the i th-node and D^+ represents the *Moore-Penrose pseudoinverse*.

(3) Compute the eigenvalues and eigenvectors of the normalized Laplacian matrix \hat{L} :

$$A\vec{v} = \lambda\vec{v} \Rightarrow \hat{L}\mathbf{v} = \lambda D\mathbf{v}$$

(4) Select the first n -eigenvalues (and their corresponding n -eigenvectors) that are greater than zero.

3.2. Cauchy Graph Embeddings

The Laplacian Eigenmaps⁴² were successful in treating large distances between pairs of vectors because the quadratic expression mentioned above emphasized more the distances that were significant rather than those that were smaller. This false notion of *local topology preserving* was explained by Luo et al., where they proposed a new version of the Laplacian Eigenmaps algorithm where the optimization function was modified so that short distances in the embedding space were also significant and *local topology preserving* was really accomplished.

$$\begin{aligned} \min_x J(x) &= \sum_{i=1}^{|\mathcal{V}|} \sum_{j=1}^{|\mathcal{V}|} \frac{(x_i - x_j)^2}{(x_i - x_j)^2 + \sigma^2} w_{ij}, \\ \text{s.t.}, \sum_{i=1}^{|\mathcal{V}|} x_i^2 &= 1, \sum_{i=1}^{|\mathcal{V}|} x_i = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The previous expression can be simplified with the following operations:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_x \sum_{i=1}^{|\mathcal{V}|} \sum_{j=1}^{|\mathcal{V}|} \frac{(x_i - x_j)^2}{(x_i - x_j)^2 + \sigma^2} w_{ij} &= \\ \min_x \left(1 - \sum_{i=1}^{|\mathcal{V}|} \sum_{j=1}^{|\mathcal{V}|} \frac{\sigma^2}{(x_i - x_j)^2 + \sigma^2} w_{ij} \right) &= \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \max_x \sum_{i=1}^{|\mathcal{V}|} \sum_{j=1}^{|\mathcal{V}|} \frac{\sigma^2}{(x_i - x_j)^2 + \sigma^2} w_{ij} = \\ \max_x \sum_{i=1}^{|\mathcal{V}|} \sum_{j=1}^{|\mathcal{V}|} \frac{w_{ij}}{(x_i - x_j)^2 + \sigma^2} \end{aligned}$$

Expressed in a general δ -dimensional embedding, we conclude:

$$\begin{aligned} \max_R J(R) = \sum_{i=1}^{|\mathcal{V}|} \sum_{j=1}^{|\mathcal{V}|} \frac{w_{ij}}{\|r_i - r_j\|^2 + \sigma^2} \quad (5) \\ \text{s.t.}, RR^T = I, Re = \bar{0} \end{aligned}$$

Optimizing Equation (5) allows us to compute the Cauchy Embedding of a given weighted graph. The authors of the original paper proposed an iterative algorithm that converges with the embedding solution after a few iterations. The embedding dimension is one of the key hyperparameters of the CGE algorithm. It is freely selectable, although typically representable dimensions (2D and 3D) are chosen, as they not only leverage embedding techniques but also allow for data visualization. The selection of the desired dimensions follows a process similar to Laplacian Eigenmaps, where the first n -eigenvalues and their corresponding n -eigenvectors greater than zero are selected. The desired embedding dimensions are then chosen in ascending order, akin to the approach used in PCA when selecting a subset of the principal components.

3.3. Distance Correlation

The distance correlation⁴³ is a metric that measures the statistical dependence between two vectors of arbitrary and not necessarily equal dimensions. It is established that if the correlation coefficient is equal to zero, then the two random vectors are independent. Based on these principles, distance correlation enables the detection of both linear and nonlinear associations. Compared to Pearson's correlation, distance correlation offers a more flexible framework, as Pearson's method can only capture linear dependencies between two random variables.

To understand the fundamentals of distance correlation, it is necessary first to define distance covariance, which is essential for calculating the final metric. Consider two vectors whose values are the result

of sampling two random variables, X and Y . The first step in computing distance covariance involves calculating distance matrices (6):

$$\begin{aligned} a_{jk} &= \|\mathbf{X}_j - \mathbf{X}_k\| : j, k \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\} \\ b_{jk} &= \|\mathbf{Y}_j - \mathbf{Y}_k\| : j, k \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\} \quad (6) \end{aligned}$$

where $\|\lambda\|$, $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^n$ denotes the Euclidean norm. Then doubly-centered distances must be computed for each element of the distance matrices:

$$\begin{aligned} A_{jk} &\leftarrow a_{jk} - \bar{a}_j - \bar{a}_k + \bar{a}.. \\ B_{jk} &\leftarrow b_{jk} - \bar{b}_j - \bar{b}_k + \bar{b}.. \\ \bar{a}_j &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n a_{ji}, \quad \bar{a}_k = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n a_{ik} \quad (7) \\ \bar{a}.. &= \frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n a_{ij}, \quad \bar{b}.. = \frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n b_{ij} \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the distance covariance is computed as equation 8 states:

$$dCov_n^2(X, Y) \triangleq \frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^n A_{jk} B_{jk} \quad (8)$$

Distance covariance can also be defined, as shown in (9).

$$dCov_n^2(X, Y) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^{p+q}} \frac{|\varphi_{X,Y}(s, t) - \varphi_X(s)\varphi_Y(t)|^2}{c_p c_q |s|_p^{1+p} |t|_q^{1+q}} dt ds \quad (9)$$

where $\varphi_{X,Y}(s, t)$, $\varphi_X(s)$ and $\varphi_Y(t)$ are the characteristic functions of (X, Y) , X and Y , p and q denote the Euclidean dimension of X and Y . On the other hand, c_p and c_q are constants. Having defined the distance covariance, we proceed to define the distance variance as shown in Equation 10.

$$dVar_n^2(X) = dCov_n^2(X, X) = \frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^n A_{jk}^2 \quad (10)$$

With all components now computed, we proceed to define the formula for distance correlation, following the structural framework of Pearson's correlation (11).

$$dCorr_{(X, Y)}^2 = \frac{dCov_n^2(X, Y)}{\sqrt{dVar_n^2(X) dVar_n^2(Y)}} \quad (11)$$

The authors of distance correlation outlined a set of relevant properties in their paper, among which we highlight the following.

- (1) $0 \leq dCorr(X, Y) \leq 1$
- (2) $dCorr(X, Y) = 0$ iff X and Y are independent
- (3) $dCorr(X, Y) = 1$ implies that $Y = A + bCX$ where A represents some vector, b represents a scalar and C represents an orthonormal matrix.

Recent studies explore newer properties of distance covariance (and correlation) and find similarities with Pearson’s correlation metric.⁴⁴ In figure 1, we observe various data distributions (following linear and non-linear patterns), which illustrate the results obtained from Pearson’s correlation and distance correlation.

As can be observed, distance correlation tends toward 1 when the correlation exhibits linear characteristics (property 3), while non-linear relationships are still captured, albeit with lower intensity. Compared to Pearson’s correlation, nonlinear relationships are better detected by distance correlation, as seen in figure 1, where Pearson produces a risky linear correlation value for the data distribution (which follows the polynomial $P(x) = x^3$).

4. Distance-Correlation Feature Space

In this paper, we propose what we refer to as the Distance-Correlation Feature Space (DCFS), which will be used below. The goal of DCFS is to represent the variables (attributes) of a problem in a Euclidean space, enabling the application of conventional Machine Learning algorithms. The DCFS must preserve the property described in Equation (2) once it has been represented as an embedding. The purpose of representing the variables as vectors in the space is that if the property (2) is maintained, the relationships selected to construct the embedding will be quantifiable in terms of distance. The procedure we propose to represent the variables as an embedding involves the following steps (shown in Figure 2):

First, it is necessary to construct a weighted graph $G = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}, W)$ where the set of vertices \mathcal{V} represents the variables in the problem, and the set of edges \mathcal{E} represents the relationships between these variables. This requires building an adjacency matrix in which “all-to-all” relationships are studied,

resulting in a fully connected graph of type \mathbb{K}_n where the edges are weighted (the weights are stored in the weighted adjacency matrix W). The relationships between variables (edges) must be numerical values that quantify the intensity (initially, both negative and positive considerations are taken into account) of those relationships.

Originally, the methodology proposed in³⁶ did not formally establish which metric should be used to assign weights to the edges of the graph, although Pearson and Spearman correlations were suggested as ways to measure the relationships between relevant attributes to quantify how important the variables are relative to the target variable, as well as how related the variables are to each other.

However, in the current proposal, we unconditionally establish the use of distance correlation as the fundamental metric for constructing the weighted graph adjacency matrix A (12).

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} dCorr(X_1, X_1) & \dots & dCorr(X_1, X_n) \\ dCorr(X_2, X_1) & \dots & dCorr(X_2, X_n) \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ dCorr(X_n, X_1) & \dots & dCorr(X_n, X_n) \end{pmatrix} \quad (12)$$

The properties outlined in the previous section of this document provide the rationale for using distance correlation as the fundamental metric. Specifically, the ability to capture both linear and non-linear relationships surpasses the use of Pearson’s correlation as a metric. Additionally, the property that describes the range of values returned by distance correlation is highly significant. In Pearson’s correlation, the values are restricted to a bounded interval between -1 and +1, implying the possibility of obtaining negative correlations. In the context of graph construction, this results in edges with negative weights.

If property (2) must be satisfied in all cases, a negative edge weight would naturally imply a lower value than a positive one, which would lead to the vertices being represented as widely separated in the embedding space. However, two variables that are highly negatively correlated are still highly relevant to the problem, as the correlation is significant despite showing an inverse relationship. Representing these vertices as far apart in the embedding space would imply the elimination of their relationship, since negative distances do not exist in such

Figure 1. Examples of distance correlation: (a) linear, (b) quadratic, (c) cubic, (d) sinusoidal.

Figure 2. Distance-Correlation Feature Space pipeline.

spaces. Therefore, a significant quantitative separation would imply no relationship between attributes, which is inaccurate when considering the original graph information.

The authors of³⁶ propose squaring the individual values in the correlation matrix, which ostensibly resolves the issue of negative edges. This approach effectively treats a negative correlation c_{ij}^- as identical to a positive correlation c_{kl}^+ of the same magnitude $|c_{ij}| = |c_{kl}|$, thus removing the original information provided by the correlation matrix. In contrast, distance correlation returns values bounded within the interval $[0, 1]$, eliminating the need for external transformations of the adjacency matrices and thus completely avoiding the loss of original information.

The relationship between the values returned by distance correlation and conditional dependence is particularly valuable in the context of the subsequent explainability to be applied to the DCFS embeddings. For example, groups of variables that are closely positioned in the embedding space not only exhibit some form of correlation, but may also suggest potential probabilistic dependence, which could offer insights into possible cause-and-effect explanations.

The second and final step in constructing a DCFS involves applying the Cauchy Graph Embedding (CGE) algorithm to the adjacency matrix built using the distance correlation metric. There is the possibility of using alternatives to the CGE algo-

rithm, such as variations of Laplacian Eigenmaps. The rationale behind selecting the CGE algorithm is that the authors of the original paper guarantee better preservation of distant relationships (edges with higher weights), a feature that Laplacian Eigenmaps were unable to achieve correctly.

5. Dimensionality reduction algorithm

The second contribution of this paper consists of a dimensionality reduction algorithm that is based on the previously defined D CFS. This algorithm provides a method for reducing the dimensionality of a given problem (both classification and regression) based on transformations of the original attributes, utilizing the information provided by the DCFS as “guidance” for the fusion process that will yield the new attributes. The algorithm comprises the following steps:

- (1) First, apply *k-Means* clustering and the *Calinski-Harabasz* index,⁴⁵ which can be computed as follows:

$$s = \frac{Tr(B_k)}{Tr(W_k)} \times \frac{n_E - k}{k - 1}$$

$$W_k = \sum_{q=1}^k \sum_{x \in C_q} (x - c_q)(x - c_q)^T$$

$$B_k = \sum_{q=1}^k n_q (c_q - c_E)(c_q - c_E)^T$$

Where n_E represents the number of instances of a given set of data E , that has been clustered in k -groups. C_q represents the set of instances that form the q^{th} -cluster, c_q represents the centroid of the q^{th} -cluster, c_E represents the centroid of the whole set of data E and n_q is the number of instances of the q^{th} -cluster. The $Tr(\cdot)$ refers to the trace operator. This metric will be used to determine the optimal number of clusters (excluding the target variable during the clustering process). It is important to notice that the *k-Means* algorithm is only applied to the input variables, and doesn't build groups with the target variable.

- (2) For each identified group, calculate the inverse of the Euclidean distance from each instance within the cluster to the target variable (a very small constant ϵ should be added to the denominator

to prevent division by zero):

$$I_i^q = \frac{1}{d_i^q + \epsilon}$$

$$d_i^q = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^{\delta} (x_{ij}^q - t_j)^2}$$

Where I_i^q represents the inverse of the distance, d_i^q represents the euclidean distance between a point x_i^q and the target variable t .

- (3) Using the sum of the inverse distances for each group, a weighting factor is calculated for each instance, assigning a higher weight to those closer to the target variable and vice versa:

$$f_i^q = \frac{I_i^q}{I^q} = \frac{I_i^q}{\sum_{i \in C_q} I_i^q}$$

- (4) By scaling the original variables of the problem (outside the DCFS) into a $[0, 1]$ range (using *Min-Max scaling*), a weighted linear combination is performed using the weights derived from the embedding information to create a new merged variable for each group of variables resulting from the clustering process:

$$\mathbf{X}_{scaled}^{(i)} = \frac{\mathbf{X}^{(i)} - \mathbf{X}_{min}^{(i)}}{\mathbf{X}_{max}^{(i)} - \mathbf{X}_{min}^{(i)}}$$

$$\mathbf{X}_{new}^{(q)} = \sum_{i \in C_q} f_i^q \mathbf{X}_{scaled}^{(i)}$$

$$\mathbf{X}^{(i)} = \begin{bmatrix} x_0^{(i)} \\ x_1^{(i)} \\ \vdots \\ x_{n-1}^{(i)} \end{bmatrix}$$

The underlying concept of the algorithm is to apply dimensionality reduction while sacrificing minimal predictive quality in the models used on the data. Representing the topology in the form of an embedding allows the relationships between variables to be mapped as distances in a Euclidean space (Figure 3), enabling the application of the *k-means* clustering algorithm, which supports the variable fusion phase described earlier. The information provided by the DCFS enables the calculation of the coefficients that will weight the fusion of the original variables.

Figure 3. Euclidean distances between the embedding variables and the target in the DCFs.

The purpose of using the inverse of distance as a weighting factor is to assign greater importance to variables that are closer to the target variable and less importance to those farther away (Figure 4). One might initially argue that this procedure could be directly carried out using the distance correlation coefficients, thereby avoiding the embedding computation. Although this might provide a method for performing a weighted fusion without representing the variables in the DCFs, the rationale for using the DCFs lies in the complex information provided by a δ -dimensional embedding, as opposed to what can be derived from a correlation matrix. The embedding computation is based on the “all-to-all” relationships, not solely on variable-target relationships. This means that the final positioning of the vectors (points) in the embedding is conditioned by chained information, which, although implicitly present in the distance correlation matrix, is not directly actionable.

Figure 4. Inverse distance with respect to the target variable (which will serve as the weighting factor used in the variable fusion process).

It is also important to emphasize that the reduction in dimensionality is achieved through the

groups of variables identified in the embedding, ensuring that the linear combination during the fusion process is performed exclusively locally within the instances belonging to each corresponding group. This is something that cannot be directly achieved using only the distance correlation matrix. Furthermore, if a problem with n -variables is clustered into exactly n -groups, it means that each group has a cardinality of one, making the fusion trivial and translating into preservation of the original space (see Figure 5). In other words, the variables are not sufficiently related to one another to justify dimensionality reduction, and thus it is recommended to retain them for the model training process used to solve the problem.

Figure 5. Trivial example of a fusion that does not transform the original input space.

The computational cost of the proposed algorithm is mainly determined by the pipeline bottleneck, which extends from DCFs generation to dimensionality reduction calculation. This bottleneck is, without a doubt, the calculation of the Distance Correlation, as it incurs a computational cost of $\mathcal{O}(d \cdot n^2)$ for each element included in the Distance Correlation matrix. Mathematically developing this:

$$\text{For each } A_{jk} \text{ and } B_{jk} \Rightarrow T(n) \in \mathcal{O}(d \cdot n^2)$$

$$\text{Cost of } dCov_n^2(X, Y) \Rightarrow T(n) \in \mathcal{O}(n^2)$$

$$\text{For each } A_{ij} \text{ (dCorr matrix)} \Rightarrow$$

$$T(n) \in \max\{\mathcal{O}(d \cdot n^2), \mathcal{O}(n^2)\} = \mathcal{O}(d \cdot n^2) \mid d \geq 1$$

$$\text{Computation of } A \Rightarrow T(n) \in \mathcal{O}(p^2 \cdot d \cdot n^2)$$

Where n represents the number of instances in the sample, d represents the dimensions of each element of the sample (which, in our case, is always $d = 1$), and p denotes the number of variables (that is, the attributes of the problem). Given that $d =$

1, the computational complexity can be simplified to $\mathcal{O}(p^2n^2)$.

Although this represents a considerably high computational cost, especially for problems with a very large n (number of instances), a feasible approach is to perform a subsampling of the original dataset. This subsample should be randomly selected while maintaining statistical representativeness of the population, thus significantly reducing execution time. Another optimization stems from the parallelizable nature of the Distance Correlation computation, as all its steps involve independent operations that can be executed concurrently. Finally, in extreme cases, the construction proposed by³⁶ (alternative approaches will be discussed subsequently in this article) can be used. Although this alternative does not fully capture all relationships that Distance Correlation does, it enables a far more computationally efficient calculation of the correlation matrix.

To achieve an efficient implementation, pre-existing versions of the k-means algorithm and the Calinski-Harabasz index from the scikit-learn library were used in conjunction with the foundational NumPy library, which facilitates convenient operations on vectors (arrays). Consequently, the logic of the algorithm is reduced to programming the search for the optimal number of clusters (that is, the value that maximizes the Calinski-Harabasz index) in conjunction with computing the inverse of the distances in the embedding space, which is subsequently used to scale the normalized columns (via MinMax normalization) during the fusion process.

6. Experimental results

The experimental section presents results from two well-known public datasets: OASIS-2^{24,25} dataset and the UDS (Uniform Data Set) dataset from the National Alzheimer’s Coordinating Center (NACC).²⁶⁻²⁸ The former has been selected for its size, which allows one to show step-by-step results of the novel method. For a more complex dataset validation (in terms of the number of instances and variables), the second data set was used. In this case, the final results of the clustering are shown, and conclusions will be drawn.

The algorithm proposed in this paper not only enables dimensionality reduction, but also provides additional information on variables that behave similarly when iterating the clustering algorithm while

adjusting the ‘ k ’ hyperparameter. Furthermore, the weighting factors themselves provide valuable information by assigning an intragroup relevance (importance) score to each variable.

6.1. OASIS-2 dataset

The OASIS-2 data set,^{24,25} which was used in the paper,³⁶ contains labeled information on dementia patients, healthy individuals, and converters (patients initially diagnosed as healthy, but eventually exhibiting dementia characteristics). The dataset comprises a limited number of both instances and attributes, making dimensionality reduction not strictly necessary given current computational capacity.

The experimental procedure involves computing the DCFS for the set of attributes (input space) of the OASIS-2 dataset, followed by the application of the dimensionality reduction algorithm. During this process, the weighting factors from the fusion will be stored and an analysis will be performed to determine which variables formed the groups that were reduced into new attributes and which variables, if any, retained their original form due to the lack of significant correlation with other variables in the problem. The dimensionality reduction algorithm is applied to a training set derived from the original dataset, thus preventing “data leakage” or the injection of knowledge into the test set. The partitioning is performed at the beginning of the process, with 80% allocated for training and 20% for testing.

The dataset contains 15 attributes (as described in Table 1), among which is the target variable “*Group*”, which takes the values “*Demented*”, “*Non-demented*” and “*Converted*” (It represents those patients who were initially classified as non-demented but ultimately met the criteria for a dementia diagnosis). The dataset includes a total of 373 instances, which means that, as mentioned previously, the problem is of relatively modest dimensions.

Figure 6. Adjacency matrix weighted with the distance correlation metric. Each position in the matrix corresponds to the distance correlation value between pairs of attributes. In particular, the relationship observed between the target variable and the remaining attributes serves as an initial approach to understanding the significance that these attributes will have in the classification model.

Variables “*Subject ID*”, “*MRI ID*”, “*Visit*”, and “*Hand*” were initially discarded due to their irrelevance in the context of the problem or because they exhibited minimal variance in the data (e.g., all patients were right-handed). Various classification models were trained to evaluate the discrepancy between models that use all original variables and those that rely exclusively on the variables resulting from the fusion process. After performing the corresponding calculation of the adjacency matrix of the graph, the results shown in Figure 6 were obtained.

In Figure 6, we can observe a square matrix with values similar to those obtained by the authors of,³⁶ with the particular distinction that the matrix produced through the DCFS computation method produces values that are always positive and bounded between 0 and 1. A strong dependency between the variables “*eTIV*” and “*ASF*” is evident, which was also discussed in the aforementioned paper. Although it may not seem critical at first glance, the removal of distance correlations of value 1.0 on the matrix diagonal was performed as a preprocessing step prior to computing the embedding.

Figure 7. Simplified representation of the adjacency matrix in a graph form.

The representation of the adjacency matrix as a topology (graph) is shown in Figure 7. To generate this representation, although the resulting graph from the matrix is of complete \mathbb{K}_n type, only edges with weights greater than 0.05 were filtered (during the embedding calculation, all edges of the graph were preserved). As observed in the Figure, the node “*MR Delay*” is completely disconnected, which in the context of the problem indicates that its correlation is below 0.05, rendering this attribute an independent element that will not provide relevant information to the classifiers. Although at this point we could manually eliminate “*MR Delay*” based on available information, it was decided to retain it to avoid adding additional steps outside of the previously defined algorithm. The rest of the topology shows considerable edge density, indicating relationships between attribute pairs and attribute chains (for example, the relationship between “*Age*” and “*nWBV*” also causes Age to be partially related to “*MMSE*” or “*Group*”). By applying the Cauchy Graph Embedding (CGE) algorithm, the corresponding embedding for the DCFS was obtained (Figure 8).

Table 1. OASIS-2 attributes description.

Name	Description
Subject ID	ID of the patient.
MRI ID	ID for patient's MRI image.
Group	Target variable (to predict).
Visit	Number of visits where diagnosis was made.
MR Delay	Delay between the excitation of the hydrogen nuclei and the MRI signal.
Gender	Gender (M or F).
Hand	The predominant hand of the patients.
Age	Patient's age.
EDUC	Years of education.
SES	Socio-economic status.
MMSE	Mini Mental State Examination.
CDR	The Clinical Dementia Rating.
eTIV	Estimated total intracranial volume (eTIV) in cubic millimeters.
nWBV	Normalized whole-brain volume.
ASF	The atlas scaling factor studies to gauge the extent of brain atrophy.

Figure 8. Dementia variables represented in the DCFS. The $E0$ and $E1$ axes represent the components of the two-dimensional embedding. It can be observed how the information from the matrix has been captured in the construction of the DCFS, with smaller distances between more correlated attributes.

In the embedding obtained, the dimensionality reduction algorithm was applied, executing multiple rounds of the k -means algorithm and calculating the Calinski-Harabasz index in each round. This provides the basis for selecting the optimal number of clusters and their corresponding configurations. The evolution of the results obtained using the Calinski-Harabasz index across different rounds is shown in Figure 9.

In Figure 9, it can be seen that the optimal number of clusters is nine. It is important to note that

the Calinski-Harabasz index is not bounded within a range of values, such as 0 and 1, which makes it challenging to interpret the overall quality of a clustering configuration. However, locally, within the same problem, the goal is always to choose the number of clusters that maximizes the CH index, regardless of whether the nature and dispersion of the data in the hyper-space genuinely allow for a significantly good grouping.

Figure 9. Calinski-Harabasz evolution throughout the different runs. The point that maximizes the CH index is selected from the entire history displayed in the figure as the optimal value for the hyperparameter ‘ k ’.

Another detail to consider is that the k -means algorithm may converge to groups containing exactly zero instances. This phenomenon does occur in the current problem, where the optimal number of clusters is nine, but only six of them contain at least one instance. When this happens, the approach is simply to disregard those clusters that contain no information (no instances).

Figure 10. Optimal cluster assignment over the DCFS. The different clusters are denoted by distinct color assignments.

Figure 11. Attribute fusion results. The weighted merged groups become the variables denoted by ‘X’. Note that groups with a single attribute will not generate new variables from the fusion and will retain their original meaning.

With the clusters configured, the fusion of attributes is performed within groups containing at least two instances or more. The results of the attribute fusion are shown in figure 11, where the fused attributes are marked by ‘X’.

It can be observed that in the case of “*CDR*” and “*MMSE*” a new vector is generated in the embedding that almost overlaps with the target variable. This phenomenon does not necessarily indicate

an improvement in the quality of classification models but highlights that “*CDR*” and “*MMSE*” can be linearly combined to achieve a high correlation with the target variable. As mentioned earlier in this paper, the factors computed during the fusion process allow us to assign weights (importance) to the different attributes that are part of the local fusion in a given cluster. These factors are shown in Table 2, where attributes are grouped by their respective cluster assignment and compared with the importance assigned to the variables by the Random Forest classification algorithm, allowing for an assessment of the absolute importance determined by the distances in the embedding space relative to the importance established by Random Forest.

It is clearly observed that the variables “*CDR*” and “*MMSE*” have the strongest relationship with the target variable, as previously mentioned in the paper by Zubasti et al. However, by using distance correlation as the metric to construct the embedding (DCFS), the deployment of vectors in space changes significantly compared to the results obtained by the authors of the paper. This is expected as distance correlation captures more complex relationships between variables and does not require squaring the elements of the correlation matrix, which previously penalized smaller correlations excessively.

Finally, the application of normalized weights to perform the corresponding weighted linear combination generated the new dataset values, which were used to train a Random Forest (RF) model and a Gradient Boosting Trees (GBT) model. These models were evaluated based on the loss of quality in terms of accuracy, F1-score, recall, and precision (the results are shown in Table 3). Data partitioning was 80% for the training set and 20% for the test set.

The results obtained from the RF and GBT models are essentially identical, with minimal losses in some cases and slight, insignificant gains in others. Specifically, for the RF model, the loss in terms of accuracy is **-0.0134**, indicating a **1.34%** decrease in accuracy. However, the GBT model shows a slight improvement in accuracy by **+0.0134**, representing a **1.34%** increase, though this is not statistically significant. Interestingly, the loss observed in one model mirrors the gain in the other; however, the difference is too small to be of any real importance. Furthermore, the reduction in dimension led to a decrease from 10 attributes to a 6-dimensional space, trans-

Table 2. Attribute weights during the fusion process.

	ASF	eTIV	nWBV	Age	CDR	MMSE	SES	EDUC	M/F	MR Delay
Absolute (I_i^q)	1.1421	1.1408	3.3272	2.9019	30.8008	15.1038	1.1387	1.1524	1.5106	2.6925
Normalized (f_i^q)	0.5003	0.4997	0.5342	0.4658	0.6710	0.3290	0.4971	0.5029	1.0000	1.0000
Random Forest	0.0380	0.0353	0.0773	0.0476	0.506	0.162	0.0221	0.0393	0.0154	0.0557

Table 3. Classification results.

	Accuracy	f1-score	Recall	Precision
RF	0.8667	0.8848	0.8667	0.8306
GBT	0.8533	0.8349	0.8533	0.8206
RF (dimensionality reduction)	0.8533	0.8349	0.8533	0.8206
GBT (dimensionality reduction)	0.8667	0.8589	0.8667	0.8435

lating to a **40%** reduction of the original input space. This shows the effectiveness of the algorithm in significantly reducing the input space with a negligible loss in the quality of the prediction model.

6.2. UDS dataset

The UDS dataset^{26–28} comprises 1,936 columns and nearly 200,000 instances. The results obtained using the UDS dataset will be presented, enabling the validation of the algorithm in a large-scale problem with data and features that closely align with the complex reality inherent in the diagnosis of dementia and Alzheimer’s disease.

For the testing phase using the UDS dataset, the same procedure described earlier is replicated, following the methodology outlined in,⁴⁶ which evaluates a wide range of classifiers to automate the diagnosis of dementia. The primary objective of this second experimental phase is to compare the results obtained using conventional classifiers after applying the dimensionality reduction algorithm against those reported by previous authors, whose studies focus on model refinement and optimization. To ensure a fair comparison with the results obtained by these authors, 98 of the 100 selected attributes were retained as input space, as some features were removed or merged in more recent versions of the UDS dataset. Furthermore, the target variable “NACCUDSD” was included, which takes the following categorical values: 1 = Normal Cognition, 2 = Impaired-not-MCI, 3 = MCI, and 4 = Dementia, where MCI refers to “Mild Cognitive Impairment” in clinical terms.

The results obtained during the computation of the DCFS yield the embedding configuration depicted in Figure 12.

Figure 12. The resulting DCFS for the UDS dataset is presented. The input space variables are represented in blue, while the target variable is identified in orange.

Figure 13. Results after clustering the attributes represented in the DCFS. The target variable is marked with a star, while the groups are depicted as points in different

colors. The final result consists of 37 clusters.

As observed in Figure 12, the majority of the 98 attributes selected for the problem are located in close proximity within a spatial region surrounding the target variable. This suggests the formation of compact clusters, which is expected to facilitate effective reduction in dimensionality.

Figure 14. Resulting variables in the DCFs after the fusion process. The target variable is marked with a star.

On the other hand, Figure 13 illustrates the clusters obtained after applying the clustering phase proposed by the dimensionality reduction algorithm. The resulting number of clusters is **37**, which implies that the merging process will receive the **98** original variables and produce an output of 37 variables, achieving a dimensionality reduction of **62.24%**. Figure 14 further presents a visualization of the merging process based on the clustering results, where the positions of the variables resulting from the fusion process are marked with ‘X’ in the embedding space. Analyzing the groups that have been merged into new variables, we observe that attributes such as “BILLS” (difficulty or need for assistance with writing checks, paying bills, or balancing a checkbook), “TAXES” (difficulty or need for assistance with assembling tax records, managing business affairs, or handling other documents), “GAMES” (difficulty or need for assistance with playing a game of skill, such as bridge or chess, or engaging in a hobby), “STOVE” (difficulty or need for assistance with heating water, making a cup of cof-

fee, or turning off the stove), “EVENTS” (difficulty or need for assistance with keeping track of current events), and “PAYATTN” (difficulty or need for assistance with paying attention to and understanding a TV program, book, or magazine) are grouped together into a single new variable. This fusion has a clear medical rationale, as these assessments are reasonably interconnected in patients who exhibit some form of Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI).

Using the Random Forest and GBT models described in the experimentation with the OASIS-2 dataset, and the already mentioned 80-20 train-test split (respectively), the following results were obtained (without intensive hyperparameter optimization, as this is not the focus of the present paper): an accuracy of 77.25% for the Random Forest model and 76.49% for the GBT model (without dimensionality reduction).

Repeating the training and evaluation process for the reduced dataset of 37 attributes, the accuracy achieved was **76.43%** for the Random Forest and **75.66%** for the GBT. This represents a minimal decrease of **0.82%** and **0.83%**, respectively.

The accuracy results are reported as the weighted average for each of the four classes in the target variable. These results are comparable to those obtained by the authors in,⁴⁶ but with a significant reduction in dimensionality, which provides several benefits, including: reduced computational time for preprocessing, learning, and especially hyperparameter optimization, as well as a more interpretable framework of interrelated variables (before merging). This could assist in determining whether certain tests are dispensable, alongside mitigating the well-known “curse of dimensionality”, which refers to the vast number of instances required to solve a learning problem with many attributes. The reduction in dimensionality reduces the number of attributes, which in turn decreases the number of instances necessary for learning. In the medical context, this results in fewer subjects and tests per subject required to train models, directly impacting the time and cost associated with diagnostic studies and processes.

7. Performance optimizations for large-scale datasets

Due to the computational limitations associated with the calculation of Distance Correlation, as previously discussed in this article, an optimization is

proposed in terms of both time and space performance. Specifically, a previously proposed accelerated version of the Distance Correlation algorithm⁴⁷ reduces the computational time complexity from $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$ to $\mathcal{O}(n \log n)$. This computational improvement is achieved through the use of both AVL trees and the mergesort algorithm. Due to the improvement in asymptotic complexity, the computation of Distance Correlation can be applied to problems involving a large number of instances, thereby enabling quasi-linear scalability (see Figure 15).

Figure 15. Evolution of the computation time during the application of the proposed dimensionality reduction algorithm for different problem sizes, exhibiting a quasi-linear trend in relation to the growth in the number of dataset instances.

In Figure 15, a quasi-linear trend in the growth of computational time can be observed, as expected given the theoretical $\mathcal{O}(n \log n)$ cost associated with the Fast Distance Correlation algorithm. This growth demonstrates that the system remains scalable even when the problem involves a large number of instances (such as 10,000), requiring an approximate computation time of 26 seconds, which is considered more than reasonable for a dataset with 98 attributes in its input space.

8. Conclusions

The dual proposal of the Distance-Correlation Feature Space (DCFS) and the dimensionality reduction algorithm has proven to be effective in representing the attributes of a supervised learning problem, where variable importance can be calculated, leading to enhanced explainability. In addition, dimensionality reduction offers computational optimizations by simplifying the feature space in which predictive models operate. In the context of dementia and its

diagnosis based on Machine Learning models, this study reinforces the findings of Zubasti et al., confirming that simple clinical tests are far more decisive than other attributes in the detection of dementia in patients.

The space and algorithms proposed in this paper address the dementia problem by not merely selecting attributes but fusing those that exhibit strong relationships with each other and the target variable. In cases where the dataset contains many more instances and potentially new attributes not considered in the previous experiments, the dimensionality reduction algorithm becomes even more valuable. Accelerates training and testing times for the models used to diagnose dementia, while the DCFS serves as a foundation for identifying key relationships. This approach also helps explainability and assigns importance to the various medical tests performed in this domain.

9. Future works

Since the proposed algorithm approaches supervised problems from a general standpoint (without being specific to any particular domain), it would be interesting to test it on problems from other fields, such as industrial and engineering applications. Comparing the proposed dimensionality reduction algorithm with advanced techniques such as Principal Component Analysis (PCA), which applies linear combination operations to represent attributes in a new space, would be highly valuable to identify potential improvements and limitations. This comparison would enable a more comprehensive statistical analysis of the results obtained within the field of dimensionality reduction. Using various predictive models for both classification and regression problems offers a compelling opportunity to validate whether the performance of the model degrades similarly between different techniques. A study based on selecting the least important attributes—when analyzed from their representation in the latent space (embedding)—for elimination would constitute a natural extension of the dimensionality reduction algorithm. This would further refine both the number and types of attributes used to address the present problem. Employing advanced clustering techniques as a substitute for the k-means algorithm can produce superior results in specific cases where the cluster distribution does not necessarily exhibit a spherical shape.

Instead, when clusters present a more skewed and complex structure, density-based algorithms, such as DBSCAN or membership-degree-based approaches such as the Expectation Maximization (EM) algorithm, may provide a more suitable and accurate representation of the underlying data distribution.

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